

**Let the
dialogue
begin**

D7.3 ETHICS PROTOCOL AND EQUALITY MANAGEMENT PLAN

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101036534	Acronym	Firelogue
Full Title	Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management		
Start Date	01/11/2021	Duration	48 months
Project URL	https://Firelogue.eu		
Deliverable	D7.3 Ethics Protocol and Equality Management Plan		
Work Package	WP7		
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M6	Actual M6
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Beneficiary	TRI		
Responsible Author	Katrina Petersen (TRI)		
Contributions from	Maria Lucrecia Pettinari (UAH) Maike Overmeyer (FhG), David Martin (PCT), Mariza Kaskara (NOA), All Partners.		

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
D0.1	15/2/22	Draft	Outline Created	TRI
D0.2	28/2/22	Draft	Initial contributions, drafting of the guidance	TRI
D0.3	1/4/22	Draft	Version for review and for further partner minor inputs	TRI
D0.3	21/4/22	Draft	Internal Reviews	UAH, FhG
D0.4	27/4/22	Draft	Addressing Reviewer Comments and final partner inputs	TRI, PCT, NOA, all partners
F1.0	30/4/22	Final	Final Version	TRI, FhG

Disclaimer

This document and its content reflect only the author's view, therefore the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

CONTENT

Glossary	5
Executive Summary	6
Chapter 1 Introduction	7
Chapter 2 Rules Governing Firelogue’s Ethical Management	9
2.1 Firelogue Grant Agreement	9
2.2 Scientific Integrity	10
2.3 Relevant EU and International Regulations and Conventions	11
2.4 Research Ethics Guidelines and Standards	12
Chapter 3 Activities in Firelogue that could raise ethical concerns	14
Chapter 4 Research Ethics Requirements	17
4.1 Identifying and recruiting participants	17
4.2 Informed consent procedures	18
4.3 Ethics Integrity Letters	19
4.4 Ethics Approvals	19
4.5 Working in the COVID-19 pandemic	21
4.6 General Monitoring by Ethics Manager	21
4.7 Firelogue External Ethics Advisory Board	22
4.8 Research Ethics Questionnaire	22
Chapter 5 Measures to Ensure Personal Data Protection	24
5.1 Types of personal data collected in Firelogue	24
5.2 Ensuring Rights of individuals	25
5.3 Pseudonymisation and Anonymisation	25
5.4 Data Minimisation	26
5.5 Protection of Personal Data	26
5.6 Legitimate Interest Assessment for Project Website and Platform	27
5.7 Deletion of Data	27
Chapter 6 Gender Equality	28
References	30
Annex I Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form	31
Annex II Firelogue Ethics Declaration Letter	36
Annex III Research Ethics Support Questionnaire	37
Annex IV Anonymisation Guide	39

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Human Rights and Data Protection Principles..... 11
Table 2: Partner Ethics Approval Situation..... 20
Table 3: Personal data collected within Firelogue 24

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Ethics Protocol and Equality Management Plan Timeline 7

Glossary

Abbreviation	Meaning
AB	Advisory Board
CSA	Community and Support Action
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
EAB	Ethics Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
IA	Innovation Actions
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PU	Data available to the public
SOP	standards of practice
WFRM	Wildfire Risk Management
WGs	Working Groups
Consortium partners	
ADAI	Association for the Development of Industrial Aerodynamics
CMCC	Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
CTFC	Consorci Centre de Ciència i Tecnologia Forestal de Catalunya
EDGE	EDGE in Earth Observation sciences Monoprosopi IKE
FhG	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft für Angewandte Forschung e.V. (FhG)
IIASA	International Institute of Applied System Analysis
INESTEC	Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência
KEMEA	Centre for Security Studies
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
PCF	Pau Costa Foundation
SAFE	SAFE Cluster
TIEMS	The International Emergency Management Society
TRI	Trilateral Research
UAH	Universidad de Alcalá
VOST	Virtual Operations Support Team from Portugal

Executive Summary

The deliverable sets forth the ethics protocol and equality management plan for research ethics within the Firelogue project. It provides an outline of the ethics and equality guidelines, legal considerations, and standards. Building from these, it describes a general framework for partners to follow throughout the course of the project.

It continues by describing the research activities with stakeholders to which the framework applies. It describes the activities' purposes, and who would be involved, how they will be recruited, and how partners will aim at representativeness, inclusivity, and equality within these activities.

It then presents ethics and data protection actions and measures the consortium will take to ensure compliance with the framework, and with scientific integrity and responsible research activities in general. These include informed consent procedures and forms, research integrity compliance, ethics approvals, as well as management structures for the general ethics monitoring of project activities. It follows with what personal data will be gathered as part of this, as well as personal data protection needs and procedures, including data minimisation, anonymisation and pseudonymisation, and organisational and technical measures. It also specifically articulates a plan to ensure gender equality within the project.

This protocol and management plan is active within the project. All issues will be continuously monitored and any new issues that arise will be documented for future reporting. However, it should be noted that it is subject to modifications in order to address new concerns that arise as the project's trajectory is further elaborated and activity plans are completed.

Chapter 1 Introduction

This ethics protocol and equality management plan describes the procedures for ensuring adherence to ethical and equality standards and flags aspects that will require particular attention. To do so, the deliverable:

- articulates the policy and ethics framework through which the project understands its activities;
- describes the project's activities with human participants;
- defines the procedures and efforts within the project to identify, monitor, and address any research ethics and equity issues;
- articulates the personal data gathered and protection measures to be taken within the project;
- establishes a gender equality plan.

Overall, it outlines the Firelogue research ethics, data protection, and gender equality governance processes, monitoring procedures, and the consortium's activities for mitigating related risks over the course of the project. It also documents the activities of the project's Ethics Manager and external Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) to monitor and support partners. Figure 1 describes the timeline to develop and gain approval of this protocol and management plan.

Figure 1: Ethics Protocol and Equality Management Plan Timeline

About the Project

Firelogue is a Community and Support Action (CSA) to help address how pressing societal challenges such as climate change, social inequality, and ecological degradation are interrelated and interdependent in complex ways. The project takes as a starting place the premise that these issues require an integrated systems approach that views the social and economic nested within natural systems. Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) reflects these complexities. Thus, building resilience involves wildfire mitigation practices, resource interests, fire-prone landscapes, socio-economic

opportunities, and societal responsibilities. For these interrelationships to work, successful mitigation and adaptation to the wildfire risks of climate change must be paired with a just transition that ensures inclusivity, rights, and equality.

To help address the conflicts in wildfire risk management between sustainability, economic use of resources, and nature conservation, Firelogue will work with EC Green Deal WFRM Innovation Actions (IAs) projects to create synergies and identify conflicts in the risk management strategies, standards of practice (SOPs), and technologies. These will be transformed into a knowledge exchange and technology brokering platform to disseminate the insights and technologies developed within these projects. It will also assess the potential for injustices between stakeholders. To do this, it will employ methods built upon participatory and collaborative governance that ensure the voices of all stakeholders are heard within fair and inclusive processes.

Chapter 2 Rules Governing Firelogue's Ethical Management

This chapter describes the existing regulations, ethical guidelines, and standards that configure the Firelogue ethics protocol. It draws from the project's own Grant Agreement (GA), guidelines on scientific integrity, relevant EU and international regulations and conventions, human rights and data protection principles, as well as research ethics guidelines and standards. What is presented revolves primarily around consortia partners' conduct and practices in relation to stakeholders and research data gathered, as well as considerations of research subjects' human rights.

Following such governance, Firelogue partners ensure that project activities consider relevant legal, privacy, and ethical issues (and actions to mitigate those risks) from the onset of the project. To this end, Firelogue partners devote special attention and substantial effort to ensure that the ethical values and fundamental rights (e.g., dignity, integrity, privacy, autonomy) of these project participants and stakeholders are fully respected and enforced.

2.1 Firelogue Grant Agreement

The Firelogue consortium recognises its ethical obligations under the terms of the Firelogue Grant Agreement (GA). Of particular importance here is Article 34 on ethics and research integrity, stating that Firelogue partners will comply with the following principles:

- reliability
- honesty
- respect
- accountability

In carrying out research tasks, Firelogue partners will:

- present project goals and intentions in an honest and transparent manner;
- design and conduct activities carefully and reliably, taking into account impact on society;
- use techniques and methodologies (including for data collection and management) that are appropriate for the field(s) concerned;
- exercise duty of care for the subjects of research;
- ensure objectivity, accuracy and impartiality when disseminating the results;
- as much as possible, allow access to research data;
- make the necessary references to their work and that of other researchers;
- refrain from practising any form of plagiarism, data falsification or fabrication;
- avoid misrepresentation of credentials, conflicts of interest, or other research misconduct.

Further, we will comply with the requirements for committee opinions (Article 34.2):

Before the beginning of an activity raising an ethical issue, each beneficiary must have obtained: (a) any ethics committee opinion required under national law and (b) any notification or authorisation for activities raising ethical issues required under national and/or European law

needed for implementing the action tasks in question. The documents must be kept on file and be submitted upon request by the co-ordinator to the [Research Executive] Agency (see Article 52). If they are not in English, they must be submitted together with an English summary, which shows that the action tasks in question are covered and includes the conclusions of the committee or authority concerned (if available).

Firelogue partners will also respect Article 35 on conflict of interests, which states:

The beneficiaries must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the action is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests'). They must formally notify the Agency without delay any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interests and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation. The Agency may verify that the measures taken are appropriate and may require additional measures to be taken by a specified deadline.

In addition, the consortium recognises its obligations under Article 36 regarding the general obligation to maintain confidentiality.

2.2 Scientific Integrity

The Firelogue ethical governance framework is further based upon the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and good practice guides published by established groups concerning social science research with human volunteers. These groups include the All European Academies¹, Economic and Social Science Research Council in the UK², European Network of Research Ethics and Research Integrity³, European Network of Research Integrity Offices (<http://www.enrio.eu/>), the UK Data Service (<https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk>), EUDAT⁴, Social Research Association (<http://the-sra.org.uk/home/about/>), and the InterAcademy Council⁵. In addition, the Firelogue consortium ensures that ethical standards and guidelines within Horizon 2020⁶ and European legislation are rigorously applied.

Overarching principles, beyond what is stated above, include:

- Research should be objective and fair.

¹ ALLEA (2017). European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (revised edition). Available at: <http://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017-1.pdf>

² Economic and Social Research Council (2022). Guidance for Applicants. Available at: Economic and Social Research Council (2022). Guidance for Applicants. Available at: <https://www.ukri.org/councils/esrc/guidance-for-applicants/research-ethics-guidance/>

³ European Network of Research Ethics and Research Integrity (ENERI) (2018). Deliverable D3.1 Appendix: Manual Research Integrity and Ethics. Available at: <https://eneri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/ENERI-e-Manual.pdf>

⁴ EUDAT (2020). Collaborative Data Infrastructure: Data Management, Available at: <https://eudat.eu/data-management/>

⁵ InterAcademy Council (2016). Doing Global Science: A Guide to Responsible Conduct in the Global Research Enterprise. Princeton University Press. Available at:

https://www.interacademies.org/sites/default/files/publication/9780691170756_secured.pdf

⁶ European Commission (2018). Ethics and Data Protection. Available at:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection_0.pdf

- Researchers have a duty of care to consider responsibility for present and future science generations.
- Research participation should be voluntary and free from coercion.
- Research should provide value that outweighs any risk or harm.
- Communication with research participants should be open and accurate.
- Confidentiality regarding research participation should be ensured.
- Research should be independent, and any conflicts of interest or partiality should be made clear and resolved by an ethics manager or project coordinator.

2.3 Relevant EU and International Regulations and Conventions

The Firelogue consortium will comply with applicable international, EU and national law, as well as international conventions and declarations relevant to the domain of the project comprising (but not limited to):

- The EU Charter on Fundamental Rights (2012/C 326/02).
- The European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR, 1950).
- The Helsinki Declaration of the World Medical Association on Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects (version adopted by the 64th WMA General Assembly, Fortaleza, Brazil, October 2013).
- The UNESCO Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights (2005).
- DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/882 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 17 April 2019 on the accessibility requirements for products and services.
- The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1976) which provides the obligation of assistance and international cooperation exercised without discrimination.
- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Regulation EU 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.
- The CoE Convention No. 108 for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data (1981).
- The CoE Convention No. 181: Additional Protocol to the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, Regarding Supervisory Authorities and Transborder Data Flow (2001).
- The CoE Convention No. 223: Protocol amending the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data (2018), entry into force 2023.

These laws establish a set of human rights and data protection principles:

Table 1: Human Rights and Data Protection Principles

Autonomy	The right to choose for oneself or determine one's outcomes.
----------	--

Non-discrimination	No person should be treated less favourably than another person.
Privacy	The right to be left alone, including informational, decisional, and physical privacy.
Dignity	Respecting others' views, choices, and decisions in ways that keep integrity in the relationship.
Solidarity	Considerations in the public interest, in conjunction with benefit for self and others, built upon an understanding of commonality.
Accessibility	Ensure the unique needs (e.g., physical, resources) of individuals are addressed so as to allow them equal access and benefit.
Accountability	Firelogue partners will follow appropriate technical and organisational measures, including data protection policies, maintaining documentation of one's processing activities, and adhering to relevant codes of conduct. This also includes recording and, where necessary, reporting personal data breaches.
Right to be forgotten	The right to have one's personal data erased from records without undue delay. However, this right is not absolute, particularly if personal data is processed solely for the purpose of research.
Purpose limitation	Personal data has to be collected for explicit and legitimate purposes and must not be further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes.
Data security	Data controllers must implement technical and organisational measures to ensure an appropriate level of security for data, such as pseudonymisation, encryption, and testing of the resilience of data systems.
Data minimisation	No data which is not strictly necessary should be collected or processed.
Proportionality	Benefits should be weighed between (private/public) interests to be protected, means of protecting, and limitation of individual rights for such protection.
Accuracy	Accuracy and reliability of data (evidence, assessment, personal, etc.) is required.

2.4 Research Ethics Guidelines and Standards

In addition to the above regulations and conventions, the framework for Firelogue's research ethics governance is based on the standards and guidelines contained in, but not limited to:

- ISO/IEC 27000 family of standards (best practice recommendations on information security management, risks and controls within the context of an overall information security management system).
- OECD Guidelines on the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data 1980.
- DG Research and Innovation's guidance "Ethics and Data Protection"⁷ a document that serves as a reference point for Firelogue on ethics and data protection issues raised by a panel of

⁷ European Commission (2018). Ethics and Data Protection. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/5._h2020_ethics_and_data_protection_0.pdf

experts at the request of the European Commission. This document aims at raising awareness in the scientific community, and in particular among beneficiaries of EU research and innovation projects. The authors emphasise that the fact that research is legally permissible does not necessarily mean that it will be deemed ethical.

Firelogue's ethics work also takes into account the social responsibility principle, as explicated in the SATORI CEN CWA 17145.⁸ It applies to the assessment of research and innovation plans and practices and encourages researchers to:

- Anticipate and consider the potential consequences of the project for society and the environment, including any plausible future uses and applications of the results of the project. Take appropriate remedial action to address any (potentially) negative impacts.
- Consider whether and how the research or innovation activity could positively or negatively contribute to the interests, rights and well-being of individuals and groups, the common good, or a just and peaceful society.
- Acknowledge the economic and cultural value of local knowledge, pursue dialogue with local knowledge bearers, involve them in the research and let them share in the benefits.
- Avoid misuse of research materials and results. Consider whether the materials, methods, technologies, and knowledge involved in or generated during the research could serve, or be modified or enhanced to serve, individuals, animals, society and/or the environment.
- Communicate important research results and (potential) societal consequences to relevant stakeholders and the general public to ensure their proper interpretation, while explaining the degree of uncertainty involved.

⁸ SATORI. (2017). CEN CWA 17145. Available at: <https://ftp.cencenelec.eu/EN/ResearchInnovation/CWA/CWA17214502.pdf>

Chapter 3 Activities in Firelogue that could raise ethical concerns

This chapter presents the human subject activities within Firelogue to which this framework applies. Chapter 4 and 5 will follow with the ethics and data protections issues expected in the project along with measures to address them. This chapter first lists the activities, then describes them, their encompassing tasks, and their purposes in more detail.

The purpose of the Firelogue project is to coordinate and support the Innovation Actions (IAs) by integrating their findings across stakeholder groups and fire management phases in ways that support a just transition. To do so, it employs a series of collaborative and dialogue formats across working groups comprising participants of the IAs and broader WFRM stakeholders. Co-developed lessons will be shared and disseminated through the Firelogue platform. As part of this, Firelogue will work with external participants that represent a variety of wildfire risk management stakeholders. To accomplish these goals, partners will conduct research with human subjects. These activities include:

- Dialogue Workshops and Working Groups
- Interviews
- Surveys
- Dissemination and Communication Activities
- Stakeholder Contact Lists
- The Firelogue Platform

The consortium partners are familiar with the ethical challenges associated with social science and humanities research involving humans, given their training and previous experience in such research methodology. They are familiar with the processes needed to meet and exceed these requirements when conducting workshops, interviews, and other research activities. Any partner needing support in applying such principles and procedures will receive additional directed guidance from the Ethics Manager and EAB.

Additional Details on Dialogue Workshops and Working Groups

Various stakeholders from across the EU will be brought together with the Firelogue partners (T4.3) to collect and exchange existing knowledge on WFRM measures, technologies and SOPs (T1.2), gather reflections on diversity issues (T2.2), impact assessment activities (WP3), consultation on just transition dimensions (T4.1), synthesizing findings and assessing conflicts and synergies (T5.1, T5.2), co-developing and validating policy recommendations (T5.3, T5.4). Audio recordings, video recordings and electronic notes could be taken. The purposes of these activities are to:

- a. Map out the measures, strategies, and solutions being implemented by the WGs, IAs, and research projects.
- b. Collect and discuss impact assessments, including criteria, as foreseen by the IAs.
- c. Collaboratively suggest shared procedure, parameters, and methodology for future WFRM activities.

- d. Reflect upon the diversity of WFRM context across Europe, and in particular articulate similarities and differences in cultural backgrounds and worldviews in terms of problem framing, goal setting, and potential solutions.
- e. Identify the most relevant just transition dimensions for Firelogue, in particular those that enhance understanding of WFRM inequalities, fairness, and inclusivity.
- f. Co-develop recommendations providing measures, strategies, and solutions to overcome conflict.

These activities will also provide the consortium partners with opportunities to obtain feedback from stakeholders and buy-in for our policy proposals.

Additional Details on Interviews

As part of the survey across the IAs (T1.1) semi-structured or open conversations will be conducted to develop an initial mapping of wildfire events, relevant actors, as well as applied WFRM measures, technologies, and SOPs. It is expected that research participants will include: project managers and case study leads of the IAs as well as respective WFRM stakeholders to find out their opinions and experiences in just WFRM practices. The consultations will be conducted as semi-structured interviews via Skype, telephone or face-to-face. Audio recordings and electronic notes could be taken. When possible, for the comfort of the interviewee interviews will be conducted in the local language. The purpose is similar to the working groups: to gather an overview of case studies and WFRM actions in general, including the relevant actors, analysed wildfire events, applied technologies, and WFRM measures addressed. They are intended to complement the other activities where gaps – particularly around a diversity of perspectives – have been identified.

Additional Details on Surveys

An online survey is used across the IAs and FirEURisk (LC-CLA-15) (T1.1) to identify relevant areas for knowledge sharing and joint activities, within a more detailed analysis around the case studies planned by each of the projects. A survey will also be conducted in T7.3, Stakeholder Management, to monitor and assess the evolution of the information and networking needs and their fulfilment of the different stakeholder groups. The purposes of the surveys are to:

- g. Develop an overview of knowledge-sharing activities desired by the IAs and FirEURisk projects, placing special emphasis on their case study planning and deployment.
- h. Identify the type of data, information, and sources they are interested in.
- i. Identify existing tools that they will be using to conduct their project activities as well as the new and innovative tools they will be developing.
- j. Map the array of stakeholders' groups that they aim to get engaged in their project activities for the appropriate development of practical solutions.
- k. Understand their methodological approaches towards achieving the 2030 expected impacts stated in the Green Deal call.
- l. Map the array of case studies defined and their plans for their deployment in demonstration scenarios.

- m. identify their most relevant topics for discussion in the WFRM domain, how they will address these topics, and how they plan to contribute to them.
- n. Understand their plans for communicating and disseminating their project results and envisage the implementation of common communication activities and cooperation.

Additional Details on Dissemination and Communication Activities

Photos, videos and related footage of research activities and interactions with stakeholders can be used for marketing and communication purposes. T2.1 covers the design of discussion formats, T7.3 covers stakeholder management and WP6 deals with communication and dissemination. The purpose of these activities is to gather material that can properly inform stakeholders of the results of our project and how those results can help them in their efforts to deliver WFRM in a way that aligns with a just transition.

Additional Details on Stakeholder Contact Lists

As some activities require stakeholders that go beyond the IAs to the broader WFRM field, broader stakeholder contact lists will be built for the general maintenance of advisory board and marketing lists (T7.3), Research Integration Board (T2.5), and WP6 activities on Communication and Dissemination. This includes gathering name, professional affiliation, and contact information. Prior to any data collection for communication activities, a Legitimate Interest Assessment will be conducted to assess how necessary it is to collect contact data and send those contacts information about our project results in order to achieve impact, to ensure that our target stakeholders are informed of the results of our project, and how those results can help them in their efforts to deliver WFRM in a just manner. The project will collect contact details necessary for attending events in person, such as the Digital Annual Conferences and Joint Impact Assessment (T2.1) or in-person working group meetings. These are required for reimbursing participants and ensuring their safety in travelling to events.

Additional Details on Personal Data Gathered through the Firelogue Platform

For the exchanges of knowledge, information, resources, and technology that is intended through stakeholder use of the TechMall (T2.3) and the larger Firelogue platform and Communication Booster (WP6), the project will collect basic contact information about registered users. Currently, it is expected these will be limited to name, organisation, email, and login. These details will be necessary for users to contact each other, to maintain the integrity of the Platform, and to ensure sustainability of the coordination and support resources beyond the project's end. Prior to any data collection, a Platform Privacy Notice will be drafted to reflect all the new data processing activities. Also, the Platform Terms of Use will be drafted to elaborate on the operation of the platform, providing information to the users regarding their rights and obligations; to define the platform's liability according to the projects' needs and the applicable legislation, and to describe the terms for using the platform and the consequences of non-compliance with the terms.

Chapter 4 Research Ethics Requirements

This chapter describes a comprehensive set of measures the project will implement to ensure that the project is carried out in compliance with EU regulations on privacy and data protection, and in line with ethical standards in research and society. This chapter is focused on research ethics, whereas specific measures to ensure personal data protection are discussed in the following chapter.

4.1 Identifying and recruiting participants

To ensure inclusive and representative participants and to establish a balanced and representative sample that captures a broad range of views, researchers will seek to achieve diversity across gender, age, geographical distribution, experience level, and regional socio-economic situation. During the research, the consortium will ensure that researchers behave in such a manner to ensure there is no judgment, discrimination or bias and that they respect all people they will be interacting with.

To this end, the partners will seek a 50-50 gender balance in the recruitment of participants, preferably with different ethnic, linguistic, and, as far as possible, different professional backgrounds and ranks in the organisations. Paying attention to gender and diversity dimensions in research and innovation can improve inclusivity in society, raise awareness of differential challenges and needs, encourage gender balance in decision making, and support advancement within civil protection agencies.⁹

For the different research activities described in Chapter 3, the identification and recruitment of research participants will follow different processes. As an important note, Firelogue acknowledges that many potential participants are actively engaging in the protection of vulnerable citizens, and respects this, and accepts the challenges it will cause.

For the **dialogue workshops, working groups, and interviews**, potential participants will be identified first from the partners within the existing IAs, as these activities include those consortia partners. This will be complemented by additional stakeholders identified through literature and desk research. The partners within the IAs will also be asked to suggest community groups and other organisations that can be invited to participate in the activities. Additionally, researchers will build on their networks and personal contacts for recruitment as well as snowball sampling techniques. Suggestions by the Advisory Board will also be used, as well as suggestions from the case study partners.

The **survey in T1.1** (online survey across the IAs and FirEUrisk) will only involve partners from the IAs and FirEUrisk. However, the **survey in T7.3** (stakeholder management) will follow a similar approach as to the interviews and workshops. Here, groups, individuals, and gatekeeper organisations that

⁹ Schiebinger, L., Klinge, I., Sánchez de Madariaga, I., Paik, H. Y., Schraudner, M., and Stefanick, M. (Eds.) (2011-2021). Gendered Innovations in Science, Health & Medicine, Engineering and Environment. Available at: <http://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/>; European Commission (2020). Striving for a Union of Equality. The Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/aid_development_cooperation_fundamental_rights/gender_equality_strategy_factsheet_en.pdf

represent stakeholder groups will be identified through desk research or partner networks. Additionally, partners will publicise research activities on social media and encourage relevant stakeholders to get in touch. To ensure that different groups (including vulnerable groups) are invited to participate in the research, we will contact NGOs and CSOs that work directly with diverse populations.

Once identified as a potential participant, only people who can give prior, voluntary, unambiguous, and informed consent will be engaged in Firelogue activities. If participants are an employee of a partner organisation, they are free to refuse to participate with no untoward consequences. No incentive mechanisms will be provided, other than the potential for first access to project results. However, participants will be assessed to ensure no conflicts of interest. Overall, recruitment and informed consent procedures will be conducted to ensure no coercion is exerted and participation is voluntary. Throughout, the ethical implications of participation will be considered, such as dignity, non-discrimination, non-malevolence, and well-being. Redress mechanisms, such as referral to the Ethics Advisory Board, will be offered.

Official correspondence, including email invitations to participate, will be sent to an official correspondence source (e.g., work email accounts), and will include concise information on the project activities and a short introduction to the primary researcher involved. Easily readable information will be sent, so participants can readily decide if they want to engage or are an appropriate fit. If the person cannot engage due to time, they will be asked if they are willing to suggest a colleague or fellow expert from their practitioner community.

Prior to the implementation of the interviews and workshops, all individuals will be informed according to the informed consent procedures as detailed in Section 4.2 below.

4.2 Informed consent procedures

The consortium will follow long-established principles relating to relevant ethical procedures surrounding research with human participants, including obtaining voluntary informed consent, as well as ensuring participants' privacy, anonymity, confidentiality, and the protection of their personal data. Researchers will ensure that potential participants have fully understood the information and what participation will entail, and do not feel pressured or forced to give consent. All participants will be given the opportunity to ask questions and receive understandable answers from the Firelogue partner with whom they engage before making decisions about their participation. See Annex I for the participant information sheet and consent form templates.

Content: Partners will provide participants with information sheets and consent forms in a language and terms fully understandable to them. These forms will describe the aims, methods and implications of the research, the nature of the participation and any benefits or risks (e.g., to privacy) that might be involved. They will explicitly affirm that participation is voluntary and that participants have the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw their participation, or data, at any time, without any

consequences. The forms will outline how partners will collect and protect data during the project, store it securely, and then delete it.

Language: Partners will engage participants in their native languages as far as possible. When necessary, the information sheet and informed consent form will also be translated.

Format: The project can engage parallel formats for the participant information sheet and consent forms: paper copies or online copies on [EUSurvey](#) that can be filled out anywhere with centralised responses for easy ethics manager monitoring and data protection control. To ensure full transparency, when using the online form, information about the processing of data on EUSurvey's portal is provided both in the information sheet and consent.

Obtaining Consent: Before the start of a workshop, interview, or other activity that could raise ethical concerns, the partners will ask participants from outside the consortium to review an information sheet and to sign an informed consent form. Having reviewed the information sheet, and having the opportunity to ask questions, participants will provide consent. By default, written consent will be sought.

Special Considerations: Recorded information (audio and/or visual) will be given special consideration to ensure that privacy and personal identities are protected. Participants will be provided with a consent form to read and sign if they will be photographed or recorded visually (e.g., video) during project activities.

Storage: Paper consents will be stored in secure file storage at the premises of the partner organising the event, in order to minimise the risk of loss. This partner will promptly scan them and store them on Firelogue's SharePoint, in access-restricted folders. The paper copies will be destroyed at the end of the project. Online consents will be stored on EUSurvey until an event is over, after which they will be downloaded to the project's SharePoint, in access restricted folders. At this point, they will be deleted from EUSurvey. The access will be granted only to partners of the consortium and will be password protected.

Deletion: Upon completion of the project, electronic copies will be kept of the consents by the project coordinator for up to 5 years, to meet EC requirements, as well as to support data subjects who wish to engage their right.

4.3 Ethics Integrity Letters

To further support acting with integrity, an ethics declaration letter has been produced and will be signed by all partners, upon reading this deliverable. The template for this is in Annex II.

4.4 Ethics Approvals

As already described above when summarizing Article 24 of the GA, Consortium members are required to seek ethical approval prior to commencing any research that raises ethical concerns.

If there is an ethics committee (e.g., internal review board, national research ethics committee), an opinion or approval could be needed. Please consult with them either to:

- a) get in writing that an opinion for these activities is not necessary; or
- b) initiate the opinion request process.

If there is no board, it is still best practice to document:

- that obtaining such an opinion is not obligatory;
- how the activities comply with ethical and legal requirements in your country/EU;
- assessment of potential risks to participants and mitigation measures.

A research ethics questionnaire has been developed (see 4.8 below) and is found in Annex III, to support all partners in this process. The intention is that the Ethics Manager will work with partners through the questionnaire to do an initial assessment of the activities and to produce any necessary, activity-specific, material for ethics approvals or opinions. Documents submitted and communications received will be kept on file, translated, and submitted upon request by the coordinator to the Agency.

Each consortium member has a different ethics board situation. Many partners have no boards from which to request approvals or opinions. Some partners have internal advisors who can offer guidance on ethics related questions when needed. Table 2 below documents the ethics board situation for all consortium members.

Table 2: Partner Ethics Approval Situation

Organisation Short Name	Ethics board and approval situation
1 / FhG	Fraunhofer runs its own Ethics Department, which can give guidance on ethics related questions and may even implement Germany wide ethics councils in case certain questions are of major societal interest.
2 / PCF	PCF does not have an internal Ethics board to apply to. It will ensure that all work is compliant with the applicable rules on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices, and agencies and on the free movement of such data.
3 / NOA	NOA does not have an ethics board to apply for approval from for SSH research.
4 / SAFE	SAFE does not have an ethics board to apply for approval from for SSH research.
5 / TRI	TRI does not have an ethics board to apply for approval from for SSH research. TRI regularly offers ethics and data protection advise services to projects and organisations, building a repertoire of knowledge which can be applied if needed.
6 / EDGE	EDGE does not have an ethics board to apply for approval from for SSH research.
7 / IIASA	IIASA does not have an ethics board to apply for approval from for SSH research.
8 / INESCTEC	INESCTEC is presently constituting their ethics commission, without, at this stage, any specific advisor. Nevertheless, we hope to have the ethics commission constituted and fully operational by the end of the present year.

9 / TIEMS	TIEMS does not have an ethics board or committee. In case ethics related issues emerge, TIEMS Board of Directors will provide guidance and make decisions.
10 / VOST	VOST does not have an ethics board to apply for approval from for SSH research.
11 / CMCC	CMCC has an Ethical Code and an Ethics Committee. CMCC does not have a priori verification procedures on project activities through its Ethics Committee; it intervenes in the case of reports of activities in contrast with the Ethical Code. Firelogue activities are not in contrast with the research aims of the Foundation CMCC, nor with the modus operandi.
12 / CTFC	CTFC has no internal board. However, it is in the process of establishing a procedure for Ethical Approval; it is expected to be operational during 2022.
13 / ADAI	ADAI does not have an ethics board to apply for approval from for SSH research.
14 / KEMEA	Basic principles of ethical requirements on research activities have been incorporated in the NOA Organizational Chart (Presidential Decree nr. 62 of 1986). The competent bodies for the follow up of the Organisations' provisions are the Board of Directors and the Director of NOA. Recently, a Gender Equality Committee has been set up which is responsible for all gender equality issues.
15 / UAH	UAH has a Committee of Research Ethics that performs evaluation of ethical aspects of the University projects and research contracts and can provide guidance on related questions.

4.5 Working in the COVID-19 pandemic

In order to respect the health, safety, and well-being of both project partners and project participants, Firelogue will consider the local Covid-19 conditions in areas where research is taking place. This includes understanding the government regulations in all areas where research is conducted, as well as limiting the personal contact that is required from participants. Wherever possible, interviews and workshops will take place online, over Microsoft Teams or a similar video platform. If it is not possible to be fully online, or if interactions would be hampered as a result of being virtual, and local conditions and regulations allow, in-person interactions will be considered. Whenever this occurs, the option will be available to participate online for those that are not comfortable or not able to meet in person.

4.6 General Monitoring by Ethics Manager

TRI is the Ethics Manager for Firelogue. Dr Katrina Petersen, Research Manager at TRI, will be the dedicated contact person for any ethical concerns from consortium members and participants, and will address ethics concerns as they come up. When issues arise, the Ethics Advisory Board may also be consulted. Research ethics will be continually monitored during the project, including monitoring consent processes and maintaining valid ethics approvals from all partners.

To support such monitoring throughout the duration of the project, the Ethics Manager will regularly attend or conduct meetings with consortium partners. These include:

- Regular presence at (monthly) work package lead meetings
- Regular presence at (monthly) Consortium Meetings

- Working Group Planning Meetings (ad hoc)
- Personal Data Protection Meetings (ad hoc)
- Meetings and consultations with the Ethics Advisory Board members
- Keeping a registry of issues, advice given, and actions taken

These meetings are opportunities for the WP leaders and consortium partners to raise concerns, questions, or challenges regarding their research activities. Through these meetings, the project's Ethics Manager will track general project activities as well as establish when special conversations or additional capacity building might be necessary. This acts as an early alert process, whereby partners can raise issues and the Ethics Manager can ask questions to identify otherwise unforeseen issues.

4.7 Firelogue External Ethics Advisory Board

To support application of the protocol and management plan, Firelogue has an external Ethics Advisory Board. The Ethics Advisory Board aims at supporting partners to ensure that all project activities comply with good practice as well as legal aspects of ethical, privacy, and data protection issues.

The Board consists of:

- Solange S. Martinez Dimarco, Research Associate at the International Centre for Ethics in the Sciences and Humanities (IZEW, University of Tübingen); and
- Dr. Dean Pierides, Lecturer in Business and Management, University of Stirling.

The project Ethics Manager will flag potential issues and deliverables that will be reviewed by the Ethics Advisory Board. The Board will monitor compliance with requirements regarding ethical, privacy and data protection issues throughout the project, and offer advice on measures the project partners take to mitigate issues. In addition, Fraunhofer runs its own Ethics Department which can offer additional advice, if needed.

The board meets on an ad-hoc basis. Between meetings, questions can be asked to individual members for small-scale consultation. Meetings will likely take place between each phase of the working group preparations and activities.

4.8 Research Ethics Questionnaire

To support partners in applying the guidance on stakeholder engagement, gender, and diversity, a short questionnaire has been created for partners to concretely engage with the issues raised in the deliverable and to provide initial answers in advance to the project's Ethics Manager so any concerns or special needs can be addressed in a timely manner. It can be found in Annex III. Issues include:

- Understanding who would participate in the activities and how.
- What personal data is to be processed in the activities and by whom.
- Documenting the purposes for which data from research participants are expected to be gathered.
- Where the data is to be stored.
- Mapping the representativeness of the stakeholders within the activities.

- Methods to ensure that all participant voices are heard in any evaluation process.
- Specific ethics and data protection concerns for a given activity.

Chapter 5 Measures to Ensure Personal Data Protection

This chapter focuses specifically on the personal data protection activities of Firelogue, in compliance with the GDPR. It first describes the personal data gathered by partners and activities within Firelogue. It then describes the organisational and technical measures the project partners will take to protect the data and ensure the rights of data subjects.

5.1 Types of personal data collected in Firelogue

The project will collect and process personal data only if, and insofar as, it is necessary for its research and engagement activities. Personal data to be collected during project activities are presented in Table 3 below. Further specifics about the data, by partner, what purposes, and data protection restrictions can be found in the Data Management Plan, D7.4, submitted by M6.

Table 3: Personal data collected within Firelogue

Source	Personal Data Type	Purpose	Task WP	Responsible Partners
TechMall, Firelogue Platform	Contact information, including User Name, Email, Name, Organisation. Photographs and videos in news portal.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For users to contact each other To maintain the integrity of the Platform To ensure sustainability of the project's results 	T2.3 WP6	NOA PCF EDGE FhG
Working Group, Participant Lists	Contact information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To contact participants to invite them to activities and follow up. 	WP4	IIASA CTFC FhG
Working Groups, Workshops, Interviews	Personal and professional experiences and opinions (e.g., meeting minutes, audio recordings, photographs); contact details for participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To reflect upon the diversity of WFRM context across Europe To identify the most relevant Just Transition dimensions for Firelogue To co-develop recommendations providing measures, strategies and solutions to overcome conflict 	T1.1 T1.2 T2.2 WP3 WP4 WP5	IIASA TRI CMCC CTFC FhG
Surveys	Personal and professional experiences and opinions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop an overview of the IA case studies Consider similarities and differences in past wildfire events and lessons learned 	T1.1 T7.3	VOST CMCC PCF
Dissemination, Communication, and Advisory Board Mailing Lists	Contact information, including name, organisation, role, and email address.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To achieve impact To ensure that target stakeholders are informed of project results 	T2.1 T2.5 T7.3	NOA INESCTEC TIEMS ADAI

	Photographs and videos. Personal and professional experiences for communication purposes.			KEMEA EDGE FhG
Consent Forms	Contact details, consenting opinions, and signatures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To ensure compliance with ethics and data protection framework. 	T7.4	TRI FhG

5.2 Ensuring Rights of individuals

Participants in the project will have the following rights, in accordance with the GDPR:

1. Right to request access from the project to the personal data it has that pertains to them.
2. Right to request the project rectify any errors in personal data to ensure its accuracy.
3. Right to request the project erase their personal data.
4. Right to request the project restrict the future processing of their personal data, or to object to its processing.
5. Right to data portability: upon request, the project will provide a data subject with a copy of the data Firelogue has regarding them in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format, in a timely manner.
6. Right to withdraw their consent at any time. Firelogue will cease further processing activities involving their personal data. (However, this will not affect the lawfulness of any processing already performed before consent has been withdrawn).
7. Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority, such as their national data protection authority.

5.3 Pseudonymisation and Anonymisation

The GDPR provides the guiding principles through which entities gather, handle and process personal data. It is important to note that the regulations apply solely to personal data – which, according to Art. 4 of the GDPR, is information pertaining to an “...*identified or identifiable natural person.*” Below are some definitions and how they relate to Firelogue practices. A more detailed guide to this process can be found in Annex IV.

Anonymised data: The Firelogue project avoids, as far as is possible, the processing of personal data, in accordance with the data minimisation principle in the GDPR (Art.5(1)C). Where it is necessary to process data about people, the consortium prefers that it be anonymous data, which cannot be attributed to a specific individual.

Pseudonymised data: If anonymisation is not possible, the next preference is for pseudonymised data. Pseudonymisation is a process whereby personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information. In practical terms, it means additional information is kept separately from the personal data, and technical and organisational measures are in place to

ensure that an identified or identifiable natural person cannot be connected with the additional information. This is the case, for example, with interviews and transcripts of working group dialogues. That said, it is directly stated within the GDPR that pseudonymised data may be categorised as data that can identify a data subject, especially if information pertaining to that identification process is also handled.

Personal data: In some cases, where there is no other option, the Firelogue project will process personal data. For example, when data is collected via audio or video recording, anonymisation could make the data unusable (e.g., such as the alteration of voice recordings of interviews). Instead, if a recording is to be made, it will be transcribed in a reasonable time period, the transcriptions pseudonymised, stored separately from any identifiable information, and the original recording will be deleted. Similarly, the project finds it necessary to process personal data without anonymising or pseudonymising it for tasks where the project needs to contact people in order to complete its work. This includes inviting people to participate in the working groups and interviews, communication and dissemination work, and contacting people serving on external boards on behalf of the project. In all cases, access to this contact information is limited to only relevant partners.

5.4 Data Minimisation

Personal data will only be used for the specific purpose for which it was collected (e.g., workshop management, travel arrangements). This means that:

- Any personal data gathered and processed in the course of stakeholder engagement, other than the contact details and informed consents and ID connecting persons to their data, will be deleted as soon as practically possible after each event.
- Any personal data required for contacting a stakeholder will be stored separately from any other data regarding that stakeholder to ensure pseudonymity.
- Any personal data gathered in relation to communication and dissemination activities within the project will be kept for the duration of the project and beyond. The basis is legitimate interest to promote the project after it is over and maintain relationships with relevant and interested stakeholders.
- Dedicated storage with access rights will be created on the project's Microsoft SharePoint to minimise who needs to see any personal data.

5.5 Protection of Personal Data

All partners of the consortium will adopt good practice data security procedures. Technical and organisational security policies and procedures are in place to protect personal data (including special category data) from loss, misuse, alteration, or destruction. Partners aim to ensure that access to personal data is password protected. Partners encrypt data and restrict data to a limited number of individuals who need to access it. Those individuals who have access to the data are required to maintain the confidentiality of such information. Partners install and regularly update all security and anti-virus software in use on all of their systems.

Recorded information (audio and/or visual) will be given special consideration to ensure that privacy and personal identities are protected. In keeping with best practices for data security, interview responses will be stored in a secure location in the file system that only project staff can access. There will be no disclosive information in data files, meaning there is no risk of individual respondents being identified.

Only if necessary or required, the collected personal data will be shared with the European Commission. The Firelogue consortium may also disclose collected data to the extent that it is required to do so by law, in connection to any legal proceedings or prospective legal proceedings and to establish, defend or exercise its rights.

5.6 Legitimate Interest Assessment for Project Website and Platform

Prior to commencing any dissemination and communication work within the project, two activities took place:

- A privacy notice for the website was produced and assessed by the Ethics Manager.
- A legitimate interest assessment was conducted for the project's contact list.

5.7 Deletion of Data

Personal data will be deleted immediately after that purpose is fulfilled, unless legally required to be retained (noting that the Firelogue Grant Agreement requires project data to be archived correctly at least 5 years after the balance project payment is paid). Once data is deleted, it will be documented within the project's data management plan and confirmed as such to the data controllers/owners.

Chapter 6 Gender Equality

Under Article 33 of the GA, there is a legal obligation to aim for gender equality. Paying attention to gender and diversity dimensions in research and innovation can improve inclusivity in society, raise awareness of differential challenges and needs, encourage gender balance in decision making, and support advancement within civil protection agencies.¹⁰ Firelogue will engage these dimensions by:

Achieving gender balance in research and decision-making teams

Firelogue's consortium aims to be managed by a balanced men to women ratio. Firelogue is regularly monitoring the gender diversity among the partners contributing to the project and their decision-making roles. In addition, the project's dissemination activities will continue to highlight the contributions of women and non-binary partners and participants in the project, contributing to a change in the wildfire risk manager and scientist male-dominated image.

Demographics of human research participants for diverse perspectives

The partners will seek a 50-50 gender balance in the recruitment of participants, preferably with different geographic, ethnic, linguistic, socio-economic, and as far as possible, different professional backgrounds and experience levels in their organisations. Such diversity in perspectives will give researchers a better appreciation of how effective, inclusive, and beneficial the Firelogue solutions are and improve the quality of our solutions in line with efforts to ensure a just transition.

While the project will encourage women to stand out and join Firelogue activities, we are aware that the ability to affect the demographics of the participants in the Working Groups will be somewhat limited because of how Firelogue's WGs are either merging with existing IAs or the fact that Firelogue's stakeholders work within existing structures with established demographics, some of which still show gender imbalance. Despite this, Firelogue will strive to advance gender and diversity equality in our activities and in their outputs to shift the established imbalances. For example, if Working Group participants are majority male because of the roles selected for a specific discussion format, then extra collaborative sessions could be used to engage women and minorities to ensure such perspectives are incorporated. Moreover, stakeholder engagement and participatory approaches are being developed in ways to ensure women and minority representatives will be given as much voice as men.

Integrating gender and diversity analysis into the research framework

We recognise that gender analysis is particularly relevant to conducting research on WFRM, a just transition, and resilience. Previous research has shown that there are differences between men and women when it comes to understanding and engaging in efforts around these themes.¹¹ These

¹⁰ European Commission (2020). Striving for a Union of Equality. The Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/aid_development_cooperation_fundamental_rights/gender_equality_strategy_factsheet_en.pdf

¹¹ Hügel, S, Davies, AR. (2020). Public participation, engagement, and climate change adaptation: A review of the research literature. *WIREs Clim Change*; 11:e645. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.645>; WEDO (2016). Gender Equality & Just Transition. Discussion Paper. Available at: <https://wedo.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/gjtransition.pdf>; Allwood, G. (2020).

differences need to be considered when developing understandings of the specific impacts of any Firelogue methods, approaches, recommendations, or solutions.

Acknowledging the importance of gender and diversity considerations in WFRM, Firelogue will follow the guidelines specified in Gendered Innovations.¹² This includes:

- Engaging gender and diversity directly in the impact assessment, just transition, and discourse analyses.
- Stressing the importance of the activities and tasks dedicated to inclusivity, representativeness, and diversity.
- Ensuring activity design takes into account gender issues, including locally and culturally contingent considerations of gender.
- Developing gender-sensitive interview and discussion guidelines to support assessment and evaluation activities, with the input from advisory board members trained in this area.

Mainstreaming Gender and Climate Change to Achieve a Just Transition to a Climate-Neutral Europe. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 58: 173– 186. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/jcms.13082>

¹²Schiebinger, L., Klinge, I., Sánchez de Madariaga, I., Paik, H. Y., Schraudner, M., and Stefanick, M. (Eds.) (2011-2021). *Gendered Innovations in Science, Health & Medicine, Engineering and Environment*. Available at: <http://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/>.

References

- ALLEA (2017). European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (revised edition). Available at: <http://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017-1.pdf>
- Allwood, G. (2020). Mainstreaming Gender and Climate Change to Achieve a Just Transition to a Climate-Neutral Europe. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 58: 173– 186. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/jcms.13082>
- Economic and Social Research Council (2022). Guidance for Applicants. Available at: <https://www.ukri.org/councils/esrc/guidance-for-applicants/research-ethics-guidance/>
- EUDAT (2020). Collaborative Data Infrastructure: Data Management, Available at: <https://eudat.eu/data-management/>
- European Commission (2018). Ethics and Data Protection. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection_0.pdf
- European Commission (2020). Striving for a Union of Equality. The Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/aid_development_cooperation_fundamental_rights/gender_equality_strategy_factsheet_en.pdf
- European Network of Research Ethics and Research Integrity (ENERI) (2018). Deliverable D3.1 Appendix: Manual Research Integrity and Ethics. Available at: <https://eneri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/ENERI-e-Manual.pdf>
- Hügel, S, Davies, AR (2020). Public participation, engagement, and climate change adaptation: A review of the research literature. *WIREs Clim Change*; 11:e645. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.645>
- Information Commissioner’s Office (2012). Anonymisation: managing data protection risk code of practice. Available at: <https://ico.org.uk/media/1061/anonymisation-code.pdf>
- InterAcademy Council (2016). Doing Global Science: A Guide to Responsible Conduct in the Global Research Enterprise. Princeton University Press. Available at: https://www.interacademies.org/sites/default/files/publication/9780691170756_secured.pdf
- SATORI (2017). CEN CWA 17145. Available at: <https://ftp.cencenelec.eu/EN/ResearchInnovation/CWA/CWA17214502.pdf>
- Schiebinger, L., Klinge, I., Sánchez de Madariaga, I., Paik, H. Y., Schraudner, M., and Stefanick, M. (Eds.) (2011-2021). Gendered Innovations in Science, Health & Medicine, Engineering and Environment. Available at: <http://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/>
- WEDO (2016). Gender Equality & Just Transition. Discussion Paper. Available at: <https://wedo.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/gjtransition.pdf>

Annex I Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form

Firelogue: Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

You are invited to take part in the research and innovation activities of the **Firelogue** project, funded by the European Commission, and coordinated by FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT (FhG). Your participation is voluntary, and you are free to withdraw at any time. Before you decide whether to take part, please take time to read the following information carefully. Be sure you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve and feel free to ask questions.

1. THE PROJECT

Firelogue is a coordination and support action funded by the EU under the Horizon 2020 programme. It runs from November 2021 to October 2025. The project aims to support and coordinate the consolidation of knowledge about wildfire risk management from European Commission Green Deal Innovation Actions and the wider community. It integrates the findings across stakeholder groups and fire management, and promotes discussion via forums and workshops, leading to exchange among a wide range of stakeholders. The Firelogue consortium consists of 15 organisations from wildfire risk management organisations, the public sector, research institutions, and industry from across the European Union. More information about the partners and the project may also be found at <https://firelogue.eu>.

2. WHAT WILL I BE ASKED TO DO?

You will be asked to participate in [*insert what the participant is being asked to do. Suggestions below.*]

Interviews where we will ask you questions about your professional opinions and experiences in wildfire risk management practices. The interview will take 30-90 minutes, in person or virtually.

Working Groups where diverse stakeholders will be brought together to consider the practicalities and challenges of your work and how it relates to just and inclusive wildfire risk management.

Surveys where you will be asked for general opinions and experience in wildfire risk management.

By taking part in these activities, you will be asked to provide the following information:

1. Your name, professional affiliation, and contact information.
2. Your personal and professional views and experiences as they relate to the activities above.
3. Photographs, audio, and/or video recordings of your participation in Firelogue activities.

3. WHERE WILL THE RESEARCH TAKE PLACE?

The research will take place at [*here insert the location*]

4. WHAT WILL YOU RECORD OR DOCUMENT?

Observer notes of your activities or feedback will be made during this research. Photographs, audio, and or video records could be made with your consent. You can review any documentation upon request by contacting the project coordinator or the project ethics manager (contacts below).

5. WHAT WILL YOU USE MY PARTICIPATION FOR?

Your participation will be used to provide input for us to understand *[select appropriate]*:

- *Elaboration of case studies and previous actions taken*
- *Articulation of measures, strategies, and solutions implemented in wildfire risk management*
- *Impact assessments and consideration of diversity within wildfire risk management solutions*
- *Collaboratively suggest shared procedures, policies, parameters, and methodology for future WFRM activities*

The information you provide may be used to write articles for peer-reviewed journals and relevant industry magazines, for presentations at conferences and workshops or for promoting the project in general (e.g. on social media or in newsletters). All information that could either directly or indirectly identify you will be fully anonymised.

6. WHY HAVE I BEEN CHOSEN?

You have been invited because of your experience with and involvement in the Innovation Action projects (IAs), related research projects, or relevant experience in wildfire risk management.

7. DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

Your participation is entirely voluntarily. You are free to leave at any time, without giving reason and without any consequences for you or your future participation in the project. You are free to refuse to answer any questions or provide any information. If you were invited to participate by your employer, be assured that you are under no undue pressure, advantage, or disadvantage to take part. You have the right to ask questions and receive understandable answers before making any decision.

8. WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE DISADVANTAGES OF TAKING PART?

We do not envisage any disadvantages or risks related to your participation.

9. WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

This work contributes to future improvements in wildfire risk management. You will not be provided with any incentive to participate.

10. RIGHT TO WITHDRAW

You may withdraw your consent from this project at any time without giving a reason. To do so, simply contact Dr. Claudia Berchtold (project coordinator) or Dr. Katrina Petersen (project ethics manager), whose details are included below. You will be asked whether you would like us to delete your data or whether you are fine for these data to continue to be processed. You may be asked why you have decided to withdraw, but you are under no obligation to give a reason.

11. DATA PROTECTION NOTICE

The lawful grounds for the processing

Our lawful basis for processing personal data from research related activities is affirmative consent - Article 6(1)(a). Our lawful basis for the creation of contact lists and similar stakeholder engagement activities is legitimate interest - Article 6(1)(f). When we first contact you based on this legitimate interest, we will make sure to follow up on any request to be removed from our contact lists.

How long do we keep your personal data?

If you agree to take part in the research, any personal data (e.g. name, contact details) collected from you will be used for our internal processing, administrative purposes, and to enable us to contact you if we require further information. Your details will be kept for a maximum of 5 years following the end of the project.

How do we store your personal data?

The record of your participation will be kept in a file separate from the research data. All data will be encrypted, stored on password-protected computers, in secure locations at Firelogue partner institutions, and shared through a secure online platform managed by Fraunhofer. *[if online] To process the online consent form, your personal data will be stored on EUSurvey's portal for accountability purposes until the activity is concluded and the details are downloaded to Firelogue's secure servers.*

Sharing your personal data

We will share your personal data with third parties where required by law, where it is necessary to administer our relationship with you or where we have another relevant, carefully assessed legitimate interest in doing so. We will not disclose your personal data to third parties unless there is a legal basis for this. We will not share your personal data for marketing purposes. All information we collect about you will be kept strictly confidential unless we are required to share your information with the European Commission as part of our obligations. We will not publish any information in reports or communications materials that would enable you to be directly or indirectly identified, unless you directly consent. However, the researcher has a duty of care to report to the relevant authorities possible harm/danger to the participant or others. If this were the case, we would inform you of any decisions that might limit your confidentiality.

Your rights

You have the right to information regarding what is collected and processed, to access your data being processed, to delete or make any changes to this information, and to restrict processing. You have the right to receive requested information in a time-limited fashion. If you are concerned or have questions about how your personal data is being processed, or if you wish to exercise any of these rights, please contact us using the contact details below.

12. CONTACT FOR QUESTIONS, CONCERNS, OR FURTHER INFORMATION

If you have any questions about this research or your prospective involvement in it, please contact:

Project Coordinator

Dr. Claudia Berchtold

Email: claudia.berchtold@int.fraunhofer.de

Fraunhofer Institute for Technological Trend Analysis – INT

Department for Technology Analysis and Strategic Planning (TASP)

Unit for Public Technology and Innovation Planning (TIP)

Appelsgarten 2, 53879 Euskirchen, Germany

Project Ethics Manager

Dr. Katrina Petersen

Email: katrina.petersen@trilateralresearch.com

Trilateral Research

One Knightsbridge Green (5th Floor)

London SW1X 7QA, UK

STATEMENT OF INFORMED CONSENT

By signing this form, you agree to take part in the Firelogue research. The nature of the research, your involvement in it, and your rights regarding your participation in the project are explained in the Information Sheet accompanying this form.

Circle 'Yes' to affirmatively consent to the following statements. Circle 'No' to dissent.

I have reviewed the participant information sheet and understand my participation in Firelogue's activities.	Yes	No
I have had an opportunity to ask questions about the project.	Yes	No
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without penalty.	Yes	No
I consent to have my participation used to further develop and improve the Firelogue solutions.	Yes	No
I consent to have pseudonymised quotes be used in presentations and publications.	Yes	No
I consent to have data from my participation be used to write articles for peer-reviewed journals and relevant industry magazines, for presentations at conferences and workshops.	Yes	No
I consent to have photos, audio, and video be used in the promotion of Firelogue in general (e.g. social media).	Yes	No
I understand that the project may retain my data for a period of up to five years.	Yes	No
I would like to be added to your contact list to receive regular project updates.	Yes	No

<i>[if online] I understand that this consent will be stored on EUSurvey's portal for accountability purposes until the activity is concluded and the details are downloaded to Firelogue partners' secure servers.</i>	Yes	No
I am willing to take part in the research.	Yes	No

Participant Consent

Name

Affiliation

Country

Contact

Signature Date (Day/month/year)

Statement by the Researcher taking consent

I confirm that the participant was given the information sheet. I confirm the participant had an opportunity to ask and get answers to questions about the project and the research activity he/she will be involved in. I confirm that the participant has given consent freely and voluntarily.

Name of Researcher _____

Signature of Researcher _____

Date _____ (Day/month/year)

Annex II Firelogue Ethics Declaration Letter

I the undersigned, [NAME], representing [ORG] in the Firelogue project, declare that:

- I have been informed of the ethical guidelines and standards to which Firelogue will adhere.
- When addressing ethical issues in Firelogue, the principles of the European Convention of Human Rights, the Rules of the Convention of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals with regard to automatic processing of personal data and the EC Regulation 2016/679, General Data Protection Regulation for the protection of personal data will all be strictly followed.
- All projected activities will adhere to the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon 2020, art. 19, H2020 Programme Regulation No. 1291/2013 and EUROSTARS (Guidelines for participants Ethics). All national legal and ethical requirements of the relevant directives where the research is performed will be fulfilled. The project also builds its internal ethics guidance upon relevant EU and international ethics standards
- All ethical issues will be managed through careful investigation. Any relevant principles and/or procedures regarding privacy, data protection, legal issues, and ethical challenges will be defined and revisited during each phase of the project.
- Firelogue has an external Ethics Advisory Board that impartially advises upon ethical issues within the project.
- The Firelogue project has produced a dedicated ethics and equality deliverable to ensure partners are aware of all ethical and GDPR standards for the project. These provide details of:
 - The detailed ethics and equality frameworks that drive the project.
 - Procedures to recruit research participants, including informed consent.
 - Details of the ethics approvals sought from advisory boards, where necessary.
 - Measures to ensure representativeness, inclusivity, and gender equality in research activities.
 - Implementation of GDPR regulations.
 - Explications in data processing including anonymisation/pseudonymisation procedures.
- All kinds of data management (collection, storage distribution of all data, privacy) adheres to relevant local and national guidelines, as regulated by law, including the GDPR.
- For each activity, a contact person will be put in charge of participants and ethical issues. This person will be responsible for reporting back to the principal researcher about participant involvement, ethical, and data protection issues. The Ethics Manager and Ethics Advisory Board will scrutinize the research to guarantee that no undue risk for the participant is possible.

Signature

Date:

.....

.....

[NAME]

[TITLE]

Annex III Research Ethics Support Questionnaire

V1.0

20 April 2022

This list of questions is designed to be answered by those conducting research with human participants to help clarify the research ethics and data protection needs of the planned activities and support appropriate monitoring activities.

Activity Name:

Planned Dates:

Participants

Who are the participants in your activity? (e.g., categories/role and organisations more generally, not specific names/individuals)	
What criteria will be used in deciding on the inclusion and exclusion of participants?	
How will they be recruited?	
Are any of the participants or data subjects likely to be vulnerable? (e.g. physically or mentally ill, refugees/asylum seekers, unable to communicate in the language in which the research is conducted)	

What personal data will you be gathering?

Name, organisation, contact details	Y/N
Personal opinions and experiences	Y/N
Photos	Y/N
Videos, Audio	Y/N
Other (please list)	

What will you be doing in your activities and why?

For each "yes" please provide a short sentence about the purpose

Asking participants questions about their experiences (e.g., evaluation, surveys, interviews, working groups)	Y/N
Engaging in collaborative work	Y/N
Having participants enter personal information into our platform	Y/N
Making videos with commentary	Y/N
Participants will be physically together that do not normally work together (e.g., shifting COVID-19 risks)?	Y/N
Other: please describe.	

How will the data be used and stored?

<i>Who collects the data?</i>	
<i>Who stores the data?</i>	
<i>Who can see the data?</i>	
<i>When will the data be deleted?</i>	
<i>Is there any data you cannot share?</i>	

Mapping representativeness of stakeholders

<i>What categories or characteristics are you considering to ensure representativeness of the stakeholders involved (e.g., geography, gender, age, role, etc.)?</i>	
<i>How have you determined these as appropriate considerations for your activity?</i>	
<i>What measures will you put in place if you cannot achieve the ideal spread of stakeholders?</i>	

Ensure all voices are heard

<i>What methods are you using to support different styles of and preferences for interaction among stakeholders (so, e.g., one does not feel uncomfortable, or another does not dominate)?</i>	
<i>Are you able to have a level of representativeness amongst the project partners present and leading/supporting the activity?</i>	
<i>How will you continue to ensure inclusivity in the assessment/evaluation processes of the activity results?</i>	

Any concerns you are already aware of?

--

Annex IV Anonymisation Guide

Taking guidance from the *GDPR*, the *EU Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques*, the UK Data Archive's advice on anonymisation of qualitative data (see: <http://www.data-archive.ac.uk>), and the UK Information Commissioner's Office anonymisation guide,¹³ this guide aims to help project partners with the process of anonymisation. While generic steps, partners should consider each situation on a case-by-case in order to ensure appropriate measures are taken.

Minimise data collection

Avoid collecting unnecessary personal data. For example, it is not always necessary to record people's full names or their home or work addresses.

Processing personal data into depersonalized data

Before data can be used it must be depersonalized, unless a research participant has consented otherwise (e.g., for use of photos). However, enough detail needs to remain to demonstrate the legitimacy of the participant, to show they have the expertise, qualifications, and experiences to be valid evidence.

This can happen through a few different techniques:

Pseudonymisation: replacing a personal identifier (e.g., name) or semi-obvious identifier (e.g., postal code) with a pseudonym. The pseudonym could be re-linked to identifiers, but this information is stored separately. Thus, those using only the pseudonymised data without the linking details will not be able to identify any data subjects. In order to maintain the ability to link personal data with depersonalized data, each data piece should be given a unique identification number (e.g., 000001), which will be recorded in a separately stored key. The original personal data should be deleted as soon as possible.

For this to be successful, *all* potential identifiers need to be changed and/or replaced. For example, even if a pseudonym is used for a Senior Fire Officer involved in a wildfire response, if work refers directly to a specific disaster, it could be possible to infer who was the Senior Fire Officer. To determine if further semi-obvious identifiers need to be replaced with pseudonyms a balance of audience (do they have the knowledge to identify the person), effort (how much work would go into anonymisation), risk (harm to individual if identified), and need for contextual details to articulate relevancy of the data (to show validity of source and content) must be considered.

Abstraction and generalization: if further de-identification is needed, de-contextualizing data is useful. For example, rather than provide exact geographical locations (e.g., the name of a locality that experienced a wildfire), more general geographical locations can be used, such as regions (e.g.,

¹³ Information Commissioners Office (2012). Anonymisation: managing data protection risk code of practice. Available at: <https://ico.org.uk/media/1061/anonymisation-code.pdf>

Southern Greece). If doing this, though, it is important to retain enough contextual information to be useful for any case being made. For example, if the significance of the wildfire location was because the region had a poor socio-economic outlook, then the abstraction needs to ensure this is addressed.

Depersonalising textual data: Remove all obvious and semi-obvious identifiers. No ability to relink is provided and original data is deleted. This should happen when doing so does not limit a data subject's ability to exercise their rights.

Working with audio/visual data

A person's voice and face are recognisable and therefore personal data. Audio recordings can be depersonalized by transcribing them and by using pseudonymisation and abstraction techniques. Photos can be blurred. However, videos present a unique challenge in the effort it takes to alter them for depersonalisation. Thus, they should only be used when consent is obtained.

An Example of Depersonalizing Textual Data

The UK's Information Commissioner's Office *Anonymisation: managing data protection risk code of practice (2012)* has a series of useful case study examples for anonymisation. One example (p. 72) is shown here for reference:

Original text

Interview recorded: 3pm, 10 October 2011
 Interviewee: Julius Smith
 DoB: 9 September 2005
 School: Green Lanes Primary School

I live on Clementine Lane so I walk to school every day. I live in a flat with my parents and my Uncle Jermaine. When I get home from school I watch TV. I don't like reading but I like watching Harry Potter films. My favourite subject at school is art. My teacher is Mr Haines and he is very nice. I used to get bullied by Neil and Chris but I told Mr Haines and they stopped.

I play football for Junior Champs, and we are good. I play midfield.

Anonymised text

Interview recorded: October 2011
 Interviewee ref: 2011/67
 School year: Key Stage 1
 School local authority area: Lynenham District Council

I live in [LM51 postcode] so I walk to school every day. I live with [family members]. When I get home from school I watch TV. I don't like reading but I like watching Harry Potter films. My favourite subject at school is art. My teacher is Mr [teacher's name] and he is very nice. I used to get bullied by [other pupils] but I told [the teacher] and they stopped.

I play football for [a local team], and we are good. I play midfield.

THIS IS THE END OF THIS DOCUMENT

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020
RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101036534